

Growing, harvesting and sharing knowledge for rural futures

What is EU-FarmBook?

EU-FarmBook is a Horizon Europe project that has built a free, open-access online platform to collect and share agricultural and forestry knowledge at regional, national, and European levels.

The platform offers an interactive, multilingual space where agricultural and forestry communities can access practical materials.

By adhering to the principles of FAIR data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), EU-FarmBook ensures that users can explore innovative ways to overcome their daily challenges or gain further insight

EU-FarmBook connects you to practical tools, guides, videos, and research-based insights from EU-funded projects that work to support farming, forestry, and broader rural development.

Main objectives

The primary goal of EU-FarmBook is to **ensure that innovative results and best practices** coming from EU-funded projects in agriculture, forestry and rural development **reach the people who can help put them into practice.**

Our objective is to foster a collaborative environment where individuals can contribute their expertise and insights, thereby supporting knowledge flows within the agricultural and forestry communities.

Key features that make the difference:

MULTILINGUAL HUB

Language is often a barrier to sharing knowledge across borders. EU-FarmBook removes this hurdle with automatic translations in **24 EU languages** and **AI-assisted smart search functions**.

FARM-ASSISTANT

With the help of AI, our Farm-Assistant chatbot offers smart, **personalized search results based on your needs**.

NETWORK OF AMBASSADORS

Ambassadors work to connect the EU-FarmBook with the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) of each Member State, **tailoring their approach** to match the unique features and dynamics of each region.

FREE AND LONG-TERM ACCESS

Ensures that valuable practice-oriented materials supporting farmers, foresters, and rural communities remains accessible long-term, **without additional costs, all in one platform**.

EU-BACKED KNOWLEDGE

Access practical results from EU-funded Research & Innovation projects that address the immediate needs of farmers, foresters and rural communities. It provides access to fact-based, **non-commercial knowledge**, ensuring credibility when recommending or accessing solutions.

GROWING COMMUNITY

Contact other experts, discover new projects and **exchange knowledge and experience** in discussion boards.

Maximizing the impact of project results

EU-FarmBook thrives by sharing the practical results from **research & innovation projects** that address the immediate needs of farmers and foresters with actionable solutions.

These results have the potential to make a significant impact, but they must reach the farmers, foresters, advisors, and rural communities who need them most.

Are you a project coordinator or a partner involved in a Horizon Europe, H2020 or Operational Group in agriculture and forestry?

Register and start uploading to share your project's insights and solutions widely and gain access to:

DEDICATED PROJECT PAGES

Reduces the need for individual websites, **saving costs and improving knowledge dissemination**. Includes: project details and uploads, description of partners, events, news and discussion board.

ADVANCED ANALYTICS

Detailed insights on views, downloads, and engagement activities on the project page help to **assess impact** and refine dissemination strategies.

AI-ASSISTED UPLOAD

Uploading knowledge is streamlined, with **automatic metadata extraction** ensuring efficient annotation. AI-generated images increase the visibility of practical solutions.

eufarmbook.eu

Support Center

Help you getting started:

Scan the QR code to explore the platform, discover new features, access guidelines, video tutorials, training sessions and connect with the Ambassador in your Member State.

Contacts

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Explore the platform: eufarmbook.eu

